

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B371
 Date: 12 May 2008
 Take Off: 14:14:02Z
 Landing: 18:03:58Z
 Flight Time 3h49m56s

Campaign: EUCAARI

Operating Area: N Germany, Netherlands & UK Operating Area D

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Megan Northway	University of Reading	y
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	
6	Cloud Physics / CGPS / CCM2	Jim Crawford	FAAM	y
7	CCN	Steve Cowan	FAAM	
8	Wet & Dry Neph / PSAP / Filters / CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	Y/n/y/n/n
9	SWS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	Y
10	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester	N
11	2D-S / CAPS / CPI	Dantong Liu	University of Manchester	N
12	PAN / TDLAS / Core Chem	Alan Woolley	FAAM	Y
13	Mission Scientist 2	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester	

Flight Track:

B371 Track 12-MAY-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B371
 Date: 12 May 2008
 Project: EUCAARI
 Location: Western Poland, Baltic Sea, Germany

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
135541		Start-Up	-.03 kft	001	53'54.86N,12'17.10E
140823		ASP	-.04 kft	100	Open
141402		T/O	1.1 kft	045	Rostock-Laage
141946	142004	Profile 1	4.8 - 4.6 kft	106	
142101	142453	Profile 1	5.0 - 8.9 kft	109	From 5k'
142152		Video	5.7 kft	107	Start FFC & DFC
142453	143137	Profile 1.2	8.9 - 1.8 kft	108	To 2k' on QNH 1019hPa
143138	144147	Run 1	1.8 kft	110	
143651		Waypoint	1.8 kft	083	A46/D6
144147	144630	Profile 2.1	1.8 - 6.3 kft	010	
144225		Waypoint	2.3 kft	035	A45
144610		Waypoint	5.9 kft	036	A44
144631	145537	Profile 2.2	6.3 - -.12 kft	005	6.5k'-50', QNH 1017
145537	150219	Profile 2.3	-.12 - 2.8 kft	024	50'-3k', 500fpm
145958		Waypoint	1.9 kft	009	A43
150228	150928	Profile 2.3	2.9 - 9.0 kft	044	1kfpm, Q1020
150928	152041	Profile 2.4	9.0 - -.19 kft	045	End at 50'
151004		Waypoint	8.5 kft	044	A42
151832			0.86 kft	045	500fpm
152042	153042	Profile 2.5	-.20 - 9.0 kft	054	From 50'
152551		Waypoint	4.6 kft	043	A41/C1
153133	153209	Run 2	9.0 kft	329	
153210	153337	Profile 2.6	9.0 - 8.6 kft	331	
153517	153530	Run 3	8.6	176	
153639			8.5 kft	150	descend
153800	154120	Profile 3.1	8.5 - 5.5kft	230	
154120	155330	Run 4	5.5 kft	229	
155307		Video	5.5 kft	230	Change Tapes
155348	155728	Profile 4	5.3 - 1.3 kft	230	To 1.5k' Q1021
155728	161105	Run 5	1.3 - 1.8 kft	227	Creep above cloud
155908		Heimann	1.3 kft	226	Cal
160049		Event	1.5 kft	226	Climb above cloud
160113		Event	1.5 kft	226	Level at 1.7k'
160350		Waypoint	1.5 kft	217	A43
161110	164806	Run 5	1.8 kft	186	Above cloud top
161630		Waypoint	1.8 kft	219	A44
162011		Waypoint	1.8 kft	263	A45
162521		Waypoint	1.8 kft	196	A46/D6 - plumes
163236		WP	1.8 kft	207	A47
163707		Waypoint	1.8 kft	193	A48
164739		Waypoint	1.8 kft	188	A49
164811	165019	Profile 5	1.8 - 3.9 kft	200	2k'-4k' Q1017
165019	170012	Run 6	3.9 kft	201	2k'
170013	170218	Profile 6.1	3.9 - 1.9 kft	201	4k'-2k'
170229	171246	Run 7	1.9 - 2.1 kft	199	
170246		WP	1.9 kft	201	A50
171246	173015	Profile 7	2.1 - 24.0 kft	265	
171325		Waypoint	2.7 kft	200	A51/F10, Melpitz
171914		Event	8.6 kft	150	1.5kfpm
180358		Land	1.9 kft	043	Oberpfaffenhofen
180559	180637	Pirouette 1	1.8 kft	043	Abort, Zenith too low
180729		ASP	1.8 kft	175	Close
181246		Shutdown	1.9 kft	346	48'04.68N, 11'17.51E

B371 Track 12-MAY-08

EUCAARI Flight B371
FAAM sortie brief

Monday 12th May, 2008

1. Pilot 1 – Alan Foster
2. Pilot 2 - Ian Ramsay-Rae
3. CCM – Dawn Quinn
4. Core Chem/PAN - Alan Wooley
5. Flight Manager – Maureen Smith
6. Cloud Phys/CCM2 – Jim Crawford
7. AMS – Will Morgan
8. CCN – Steve Cowen
9. SP2 – Dantong Liu
10. SWS/SHIMS – Debbie O’Sullivan
11. Wet Neph – James Bowles
12. Mission Scientist – Hugh Coe
13. Mission Scientist – Megan Northway
14. Mission Scientist 3– Stratos Bourtsoukidis

Take off Rostock: 13:30Z
Land at OP: 17:07Z(L)

Operating Area:

Western Poland, Baltic Sea, Germany

Sortie Objectives:

In-situ sampling of fresh and aged pollution in the boundary layer centred over the UK and Europe. Conduct low level over sea for radiation if no cirrus.

Weather

High pressure over northern Germany/Denmark/Holland with lows southwest of Iceland and over Finland bringing showers and possible aerosol rainout over N. Scandinavia. High pollution over the UK predicted in the boundary layer.

Flight patterns:

1. If no pirouette was conducted during B370 during T/O or land and given clear skies perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
2. Take off Rostock-Laage at 13:30Z.
3. Profile ascent to FL090 towards point A46/D6, followed by profile descent to arrive at point A46/D6 at 2000 ft a.s.l. [24 min, T=13:54].
4. Conduct sawtooth profiles along the line of A46/D6 ->A45 -> A44 ->A43 ->A42 -> A41/C1 ->A40 between 50 ft and FL090. [54 min, 14:48Z]
5. Turn onto same route heading south and conduct SLR at level determined by mission scientist from previous profiles (suggested between 100 ft and 5000 ft a.s.l.) to arrive at A46/D6 [54 min, T=15:43Z]
6. Continue south on routing A46/D6 -> A47 -> A48 -> A49 -> A50F11 (Melpitz) within aerosol layer with possible sawtoothing between 2000 ft a.g.l. and FL090. [22 min, T=16:20Z]
7. Profile climb over Melpitz to FL090
8. Transit back to Oberpfaffenhofen at FL260 and land [47 min, 17:07Z].
9. If requested by mission scientist, perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute). [Total flight time 3 hr 37 min].

Mission Scientist's Debrief Sheet

Flight B371

10th May 2008

Summary of the weather conditions:

High pressure over northern Germany/Denmark/Holland with lows southwest of Iceland and north of Finland bringing showers and possible aerosol rainout over N. Scandinavia

Northwesterly flow over the region around Rostock and southern Sweden. Low pressure systems to the north were forcing the high pressure system to the south and compressing two bands of pollution, one aged and the other fresh into an east-west line along the Baltic Sea.

Points defined:

T/O Rostock-Laage-FLD-A46/D6-A45-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46/D6-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51/F11

Summary of the flight:

A successful pair of flights (B370 and B371) were carried out to probe two bands of pollution aligned along an East-West line from the southern North Sea to the Baltic and across central Europe. The more northerly of these was highly aged air that had recirculated from Europe, advected northward and had then be pushed to the south. The more southerly of these was fresh pollution being emitted from central Europe. The air masses had not been affected by precipitation in advance of the sampling period.

The B371 aimed to sample the eastern end of these plumes by working along a line from Oland, to the east of southern Sweden, across the Baltic Sea and down the border of Germany and western Poland. The first profile from Rostock was similar to those along the east-west leg of B370 in that the pollution was evenly distributed through the boundary layer with a scattering coefficient of 70 Mm^{-1} and a boundary layer top of 5000'. Again nitrate appeared to partition from gas to particle phase with height. During the north bound leg from the Rostock some large industrial sources were observed visually around Czstain though these didn't appear to influence the data. Over the Baltic Sea, continual sawtooth profiles showed that the vertical distribution was complex with several layers being observed. Initially, a shallow marine surface layer was seen containing little aerosol and some scattered Sc. Above this an elevated layer of aged pollution was observed with similar properties to that observed over Rostock. Showers were observed to the west at WP42. Around this latitude the lofted polluted layer became cloud topped and by WP40 The cloud layer was between 6000 and 8000'. The polluted layer extended from 8400' down to 5000' with a scattering coefficient of around 50 Mm^{-1} . A less polluted surface layer was also observed separated by a clean layer between 3000 and 5000'.

On the southerly leg several straight and level runs were chosen to investigate each of the layers observed. Initially a run was conducted above the cloud layer at 8000'. However, there was little pollution extending beyond cloud top and a descent to 5000' was carried out. CO concentrations showed the layer was penetrated but the showers observed earlier now crossed the flight track and caused washout of the aerosol as the aircraft approached point 42. A descent to 1500' heading to WP43 was carried out to probe the pollution heading south. After the line of showers (at around 54.8 N) the aerosol load recovered and over the land the atmosphere became cloud free with over 3.5 ug m^{-3} each of nitrate and sulphate observed. A monomodal number size distribution and highly aged black carbon confirm this. A filter run was conducted in this air. By 53.2 N the pollution load has significantly reduced and a scattering coefficient of 30 Mm^{-1} was observed. At this point the filters ended as the aged pollution plume was now to the north. To the south towards Melpitz bimodal size distributions were observed for the first time in the flight though no changes were seen in either gas chemistry or accumulation mode aerosol. The air was clean south of 51.8 N. A profile ascent in light loads was then conducted before transiting to Oberpfaffenhofen. The band of fresh pollution was not observed and was expected to lie to the south of the sampling region.

Hugh Coe 14/5/08

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B371** Date 12/5/08 Name HUGH COE Page 1 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					no pinnacles, some curies scattered everywhere and Bremen w/o flight plan.
14:15					T/O.
14:24:53	END P1.1 START P1.2	F1090			neph shows top of RL at 6000 ft
14:31	END P1.2	F1020			Profile as descent into Rostock F1060 lid.
					v. humid at top but cloud free, few scattered Cu but very small.
					Adiabatic profile from 2000' - 6000'
					High scat σ_{wet} 70 Mm^{-1}
					Made at 5000' zero at 6000' again everything clear except NO_3^- which goes with RH and T.
14:36					Large Industry 3 miles left.
					New lined night over head
					Cz station in Poland.
					Small peak in SO_2 , peak in O_3 too.
					New heading out into Baltic.
14:41:45	END P2.1 START P2.2				Heading pt 45 \rightarrow pt 44.

2000
20 miles north
5500
3.5 miles
7 miles

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B371** Date 12/5/08 Name MUGH CES Page 2 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:45:					On Sontooth profile from 2000 - 6500 ft and back down.
14:46:28	EWP2-1 START 22	6500' → 2000' 50'			Visually there is a layer aloft to NE next sountooth to penetrate of pass (max ceiling F1090) new in layer that 5000ft scattered Sc off shore new low below us
					NE prior to cloud 4.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NO_2 4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ SO_2 0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ PM_{10} 1.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ SO_4
14:55:37	EWP2-2 START 23	50' - FL			probe in SMPS below 100m but above aerosol mode AMS with accu mode AMS
					pt 43
					nitrate conc to 1.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ $\text{NO}_x + \text{SO}_x$ det li
					CO and O_3 high & correlated
					3.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of nitrate sulphate
					4000' NO_3^- mass
					at 53°42'
					Shevers to West on Radar

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B371** Date **12/5/08** Name **H. Cox** Page **3** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Cloud capped at 7500ft in this region
15:09:28	end 2.3 start 2.4	FL090 → 30'			descent on of south.
15:10:03					Waypoint 42 Now past shower.
15:11:30					Out of cloud at 7,200ft.
15:12:52					Drizzle Neph up 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ SO_2 and 7-8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NO_x but sampling cloud.
15:16:15					no cloud down to surface
15:20:42	EN P2.4 ST P2.5				cloud at 5500'

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B371**... Date 12/5/08 Name H CCE... Page 4 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					NO ₃ 1-2 µg/m ³ SO ₂ 2-3 µg/m ³
					NO ₃ 1.6 µg/m ³ SO ₂ 2.6 µg/m ³
15:52:23					Showers ahead as predicted holding 5500' by ECMWF
15:53:23		5000- 1500ft			Profile descent through shower at point 42 heading WP 43.
					Passing shower has taken a bite out of data
15:59:27		1700ft			around 54.8°N.
					Wedge trough line across region E-W SLR at 1700ft leading to persistent precipitation heading South across the trough line. at point 43 ish.
					Temp recovery

54.3

latitude 54.8

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.371** Date 12/5/08 Name M. COE Page 5 of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
16:14:55					Over land, light cloud CCN inc over 3-5 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ of nitrate and sulphate nano mode SMPS (nopt) (75 m^{-1}) aged SP2 all consistent, as
16:15:30					Filter run started is CO and NO _x h-CO ₂ NO _x aged air
16:25					A46 / D6 over a plate A coast Castali
16:29:26					No clear skies above with some cirrus and an inversion layer looks like to ground 70 m^{-1} of blue.
16:33					53.2N the pollution falls away of blue 30 m^{-1} . This is what was predicted by Stahl model.
16:37					and filters. Coe check laptop data
16:48:11	END RUN START P5				2000' to 4000' to conduct SUR at high humidity.
16:55					Now seeing bimodal distrib

17:00:13 4000' → 2000'

17:02:28 start run

To capture post plate phase.
Clear since 51.8°N.
Tung at 50 ft 51 (PTO)

17:18

SUR 2000 ft WASSO → WASTI
clear here, a little wind. ~~the~~
the wind generators are barely
moving.
✓ clear south of 51.8 N.

17:12:46 ed run
stat
profile

Profile ascent

✓ light loads

NO₂ peak at 3000ft

17:20 Profile

Main layer even from 2000' to 8000' (30 m⁻¹ σ_{blue})

then clear slot 8000' to 9000'

then ~~profile~~ plume peaking
at 10000ft (30 m⁻¹ σ_{blue})

falling to zero at 12000ft

pirometers not done

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B371

Date: 12 MAY 08	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
141514																T/O	
142101																Profile 1 start	
	50		1	0		0	0									FI070	
	40		1	0		0	0									FI080	
	55		1	0		0	0									FI090	
	70		1	0		0	0									FI080	
	70		1	0		0	0									FI070	
	900		1	3		0	0									FI060	
	1200		1	5		0	0									FI050	
	1500		1	3		0	0									FI040	
	1800		1	3		0	0									FI030	
	1500		1	3		0	0									FI020	
																End profile 1	
																Start run 1	
143138																	
143500	1000		2	3		0	0										
144000	1300		2	3		0	0										
144150	1250		2	3		0	0									End run 1 start profile 2.1	
	1074		2	3		0	0									FI030	
	800		2	3		0	0									FI040	
	37		2	1		0	0									FI050	
	20		2	1		0	0									FI060 end p2.1 start p2.2	
	600		2	3		0	0									FI050	
	1000		2	3		0	0									FI040	
	1400		2	3		0	0									FI030	
	1700		2	3		0	0									FI020	
	2000		2	5		0	0									FI010	
	670		30	10		0	0									50ft end p2.2 start 2.3	
	750		140	1000		0	0									FI010	
	1300		182	5		0	0									FI020	
	1200		182	3		0	0									FI030	
	1100		182	3		0	0									FI040	
	1100		182	3		0	0									FI050	
	750		182	3		0	0									FI060	
	750		182	3		0	0									FI070	
	300		262	2000		0	0									FI080	
	300		265	30		0	0									FI090 end p2.3 start p2.4	
	900		458	2000		0	0									FI080	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.4	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.4	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =0.7		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B371

Date: 12 MAY 08	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
161500	1800			5		0	0										
162000	1900		1315	5		0	0										
162500	1400		1318	3		0	0										
163000	1400		1318	5		0	0										
163500	1000		1319	3		0	0										
164000	1000		1319	3		0	0										
164200																2dp noisy	
164500	900		1319	3		0	0										
164800	1000		1320	3		0	0									End run 5 start profile 5	
165020	635		1320	3		0	0									End profile 5, start run 6 fl 039	
165500	900		1320	3		0	0										
1656																2dp turned off – noise	
170000	600		1320	3		0	0									End run 6, start profile 6.1	
170227	600		1321	3		0	0									End profile 6.1 start run 7 fl019	
170500	600		1321	3		0	0										
171000	600		1321	3		0	0										
171229	550		1321	3		0	0									End run 7 start profile 7	
	600		1321	3		0	0									FI030	
	500		1322	3		0	0									FI040	
	450		1322	3		0	0									FI050	
	400		1322	3		0	0									FI060	
	450		1322	3		0	0									FI070	
	200		1322	1		0	0									FI080	
	300		1322	1		0	0									FI090	
	200		1322	1		0	0									FI100	
	18		1322	1		0	0									FI110	
	10		1322	1		0	0									FI120	
	5		1322	1		0	0									FI140	
	10		1322	0		0	0									FI160	
	4		1322	0		0	0									FI180	
172710	1		1322	0		0	0									FI200	
173000																End recording	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.4	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.4	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =0.7		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B371 **T/O:** 141402
Date of flight: 12 may 2008 **Land:** 180358

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOGFlight number: **B371**

Date of Flight:

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	y	
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 98152
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read =26976 Blocks written = 26976 Bad reads =0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		Start = 141000 End = 180500 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size?
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images 2dc : noise 2dp: noise, some signal at 155250 + Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = End = FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start =141000 End = 180500</p> <p>Time data processed to = 165526</p> <p>2dproc files present? y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of Flight:

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size = Vol flow rate =
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Use flight_plot to check.

P.S.A.P. Log

Flight No. **B.371**.....

Date 12/05/08.....

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FAAM © 2004

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	B_a x 10⁻⁶	Ph_det levels		Run	Remarks
Set to DRS time	New filter Tr = 1.000	Set to 3.0 lpm				(30s) ? Ave = s	←Preflight
142000	1	2.75					pump on
172800	.882		6.8	14	44	transit	

B371_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

12:55:38.45 --- - - - -
12:55:38.46 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
12:55:38.46 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
12:55:38.46 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B371
12:55:38.46 --- - - - -
12:56:04.57 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
12:56:13.46 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
12:56:17.62 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
12:56:19.21 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
12:56:21.26 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
12:56:32.50 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
12:56:32.59 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
12:56:32.69 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
12:56:42.45 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:56:42.46 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:56:42.47 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:56:45.46 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
12:56:48.30 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
12:56:48.31 SWS - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
12:56:49.80 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
12:56:51.60 USH - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
12:56:51.61 USH - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
12:56:52.68 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
12:56:54.81 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
12:56:54.81 LSH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
12:56:58.69 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:56:58.70 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:56:58.92 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:56:58.97 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:56:59.18 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:56:59.64 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:56:59.86 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:56:59.92 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:57:05.55 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:15.07 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
12:57:21.31 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:21.32 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:21.35 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:22.27 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:22.44 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:26.94 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:26.95 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:27.90 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:28.08 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:28.14 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:35.38 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:35.40 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:35.42 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:36.52 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:36.73 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:41.82 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:12:40.27 --- - - - - *** cooler
13:15:25.26 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:15:25.31 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:15:25.57 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:15:25.67 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:15:25.86 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:15:26.60 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:15:26.84 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:15:26.96 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:15:30.19 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:15:32.55 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:15:38.79 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:15:38.85 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:15:38.85 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:15:40.22 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

13:15:40.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:15:40.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:15:47.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:10.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler -1 deg
13:31:17.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:22.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** 0 deg
13:31:45.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** 1 deg
13:32:20.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:32:21.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:32:21.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:32:21.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:32:22.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:32:27.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:32:53.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 3 deg
13:33:00.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction 2 deg
13:38:59.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:59.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:59.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:00.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:00.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:06.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:07.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:56:22.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** 1 deg
13:59:05.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** 0 deg
14:16:19.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -2 deg
14:17:41.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:17:41.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:17:41.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:17:42.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:17:42.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:17:48.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:17.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 1
14:25:14.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending from FL 90
14:25:26.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -3
14:27:36.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler a t -2
14:31:38.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** en of profile start of run at 2000 ft
14:32:48.17	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
14:32:48.18	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
14:32:50.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:32:51.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:32:52.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:32:53.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:32:57.18	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:33:03.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:03.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:03.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:03.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:03.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:33:04.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:08.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:33:09.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:33:12.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:12.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:12.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:13.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:33:13.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:33:19.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:47.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
14:41:56.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
14:46:31.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile climb start of profile descent
14:51:40.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** over sea with scatered cloud low c/cloud
14:55:38.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 ft
14:57:28.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
14:58:38.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud
14:58:50.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** now clear of cloud
14:59:09.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** visible layer of
14:59:20.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** pollution
15:08:00.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** showers in vivinity nof aircraft

```

15:09:29.62 --- - - - - *** end profile
15:09:37.03 --- - - - - *** deceding
15:10:06.02 --- - - - - *** a 42
15:11:58.57 --- - - - - *** bottom 2000 ft cloud filled and a lot of
structure in pollution
15:12:03.71 --- - - - - *** cooler at -1 deg
15:12:56.33 --- - - - - *** cooler at 0 deg
15:13:33.72 --- - - - - *** going through rain
15:13:48.23 --- - - - - *** and lots of sulphate and nitrate
15:14:12.80 --- - - - - *** |7 or 8 ug of nitrate and 17 ug of
sulphate
15:18:52.57 --- - - - - *** 50 ft
15:20:43.21 --- - - - - *** correction 50 ft now
15:23:39.47 --- - - - - *** cooler at 0 deg
15:25:59.37 --- - - - - *** A1/C1 waypoijt turning and continuing
profilr climb to FL 90
15:26:25.39 --- - - - - *** correction a41/c1
15:26:30.55 --- - - - - *** cooler at -1 deg
15:26:45.27 --- - - - - *** in cloud
15:29:36.91 --- - - - - *** still i8n cloud
15:30:45.88 --- - - - - *** end of profile
15:31:39.07 --- - - - - *** start of run
15:31:46.26 --- - - - - *** -2 deg
15:32:20.67 --- - - - - *** interupt
15:35:14.67 --- - - - - *** continuing run skimming top of clouds
15:37:15.27 --- - - - - *** -3 deg
15:38:27.20 --- - - - - *** descending to below cloud profile descent
15:38:39.21 --- - - - - *** - 2deg
15:41:47.30 --- - - - - *** no longer in cloud
15:41:53.90 --- - - - - *** start of run FL 55
15:48:05.08 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
15:48:09.82 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:48:09.87 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:48:10.07 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:48:10.64 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:48:11.05 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:48:15.10 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:48:15.17 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:48:15.61 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:48:15.94 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:48:16.58 USH - - - - Idling
15:48:16.75 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:48:21.10 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:48:24.66 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:48:24.68 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:48:25.11 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:48:25.67 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:48:25.69 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:48:31.58 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:48:33.34 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:48:33.43 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:48:33.66 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:48:34.16 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:48:34.56 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:48:40.24 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:53:25.62 --- - - - - *** p descent5
15:54:18.03 --- - - - - *** 42
15:54:45.32 --- - - - - *** in cloud and precip
15:55:27.06 --- - - - - *** -3 deg
15:57:28.36 --- - - - - *** 1500ft
16:00:53.17 --- - - - - *** going through cloud
16:01:02.78 --- - - - - *** 1700ft now out of precip
16:04:07.46 --- - - - - *** a 43 heading towards waypoint a44
16:05:00.55 --- - - - - *** running through a low, with a trough line
pollution to the south and a cold front
16:09:17.46 --- - - - - *** in cloud
16:14:54.04 --- - - - - *** just crossed back over to land
16:15:24.12 --- - - - - *** re-entering aged pollution which has been
pushed south by low pressure system

```

16:15:34.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** -3 still
16:16:48.96	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:16:53.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:54.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:54.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:55.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:16:55.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:00.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:02.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:02.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:02.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:03.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:03.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:09.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:15.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** waypoint a45
16:20:25.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning towards a 46
16:25:32.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning at a46
16:26:59.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** -2
16:30:03.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:30:04.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:30:05.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:30:06.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:30:07.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:30:12.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:30:13.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:30:13.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:30:17.48	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
16:30:17.49	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
16:30:19.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:30:20.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:30:21.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:30:22.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:30:23.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:30:24.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:32:36.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** a47
16:39:07.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:39:07.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:39:08.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:39:09.57	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:39:12.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:12.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:12.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:13.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:13.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:14.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:14.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:14.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:15.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:15.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:15.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:22.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:39:24.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:27.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:34.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:34.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:35.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:36.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:37.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:38.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:45.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:47:54.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** a49
16:48:03.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile up to 4000 ft
16:50:17.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run
16:52:46.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:52:47.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:48.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:52:49.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:50.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:52:53.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

16:52:54.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:55.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:52:56.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:56.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:59.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:53:06.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:56:22.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 6 and profile ascent (sawtooth)
17:00:15.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction deceding
17:00:37.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 6 and start of profile 6 down
to 2000 ft						
17:02:22.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p start of run
17:02:40.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning at a50 for a51
17:06:49.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:51.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:52.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:53.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:54.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:56.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:12:25.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb from Melpitz
17:12:32.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** to FL 90
17:13:28.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:13:30.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:13:31.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:13:31.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:13:32.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:13:35.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:17:00.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:17:02.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:17:03.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:17:04.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:17:05.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:17:06.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:21:36.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -1 deg
17:22:04.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:06.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:07.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:22:08.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:09.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:22:10.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:10.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:22:11.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:22.88	---	-	-	-	-	***
17:25:22.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:25.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:26.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:28.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:29.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:29.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:25.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** -1 deg
17:31:50.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:31:55.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:31:56.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:56.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:58.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:31:59.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:19.87	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
17:32:19.90	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
17:32:24.08	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
17:32:24.10	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
17:32:29.50	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 100ms.
17:32:34.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:36.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:36.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:37.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:40.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:42.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:32:44.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:45.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:47.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

17:32:47.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:47.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:48.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:52.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:53.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:55.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:56.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:57.81	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 100ms.
17:32:59.38	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 100ms.
17:33:02.94	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
17:33:05.50	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 100ms.
17:33:07.78	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
17:33:09.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:12.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:16.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:18.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:18.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:20.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:20.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:22.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:23.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:26.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:29.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:29.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:30.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:32.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:35:56.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** -1 deg

Flight:

B371

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS)

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B371

Date: 12 May 2008

Instruments

1. INU – not run
2. Digital Video Box – stickle brick no longer holding it up, now resting on keyboard at aft CorCon
3. FFC Window – lots of smudges, will require cleaning on return to base.
4. GIN – pre-flight position wrong. Had us over the Baltic Sea. Reset power then okay.
5. Core Chem laptop – problem with the screen, plots barely visible.

Instrument Status roundup

SWS – Okay

Cloud Physics – 2DC, 2DP minor issues, other probes okay

SP2 – Good

CAPS/CPI /2DS – not run

Neph/PSAP/Filters/CVI – All okay except no flow through “old” 10um filters

AMS – Organics not as good as they should be, inorganics good

SMPS – Okay

CCN – Okay

PAN/ Tdlas /Core Chem – Okay

Aircraft

Nil

ISDN Emails

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

Profile 4

Profile 4 & 5

From 14:27:30 to now

Flight B371 16:04:56

Heading 186 deg Speed 207 knots Height 1.4kft Press 960mb

Lat 54°30.0'N Long 15°6.0'E Wind 106 ms-1/ 359 deg

Temp 7.41C Dewpoint 6.6C

From 15:35:29 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	960.2	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	7.42	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	6.61	deg C

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B371:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Mission Scientist 1	Yet to be scanned by Megan Northway
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	No In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet
CVI	No log as CVI was only operated on three flights : B376, B377 & B378
PAN	Operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	24 Jul 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras
2 x Downward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080512_b371_141111_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080512_b371_151111_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080512_b371_161111_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080512_b371_171111_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080512_b371_181111_1hz.avi

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b371_141122_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b371_151122_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b371_161122_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b371_171122_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b371_181122_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080512_b371_141113_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080512_b371_151113_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080512_b371_161113_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080512_b371_171113_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080512_b371_181113_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080512_b371_141118_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080512_b371_151118_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080512_b371_161118_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080512_b371_171118_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080512_b371_181118_1hz.avi

Media Converter had problems with the following files :-

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b371_141122_1hz.raw
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b371_151122_1hz.raw
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b371_161122_1hz.raw
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b371_171122_1hz.raw
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080512_b371_181122_1hz.raw

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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